

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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no4**

31/12/2024

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
GA	Google Analytics
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
SoA	State of the Art
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modeling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth and human health. RAMONES will provide tools for long-term, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, propose new AI-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these can be achieved by combining SoA equipment from various disciplines in well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. Additionally, one of the main goals is to introduce novel ways of monitoring and establish response channels to inform key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals from medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies.

The present document is the fourth and final installment of the dissemination and communication activities report, introducing the fourth year's progress towards the dissemination activities of our project. The report builds upon the activities and achievements that took place during M37-M48 of the project. The scope of the deliverable is to present an overview of the results achieved concerning the visual identity, the promotional tools, the publications and the templates produced in alignment with the project's objectives. More specifically the deliverable includes the following activities and tools:

- articles and publications
- scientific events and activities organized and participated
- Environmental-, Radioactivity-, and Robotics-domain oriented activities
- web related activities in digital channels
- material and templates regarding Communication activities
- established KPIs

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All of the above are being used to maximize the impact and raise awareness, as well as principally promote the RAMONES project in the overall scope of WP5.

1. WP5 / Dissemination & Communication Tasks

1.1 WP Objectives related to Dissemination and Communication

The objectives of WP5 which are relevant to the Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities are: (i) to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work; (ii) to maximize the impactful visibility of project's work and achievements; (iii) to engage stakeholders that can support sustainability of the project via both update and feedback provisioning and can further empower the vision around the scientific domain communities, and (iv) to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to 3rd parties activating esp. in H2020 and Environmental Intelligence landscape.

The WP is organized into six (6) tasks, from which the four (4) most relevant to the dissemination and outreach activities are presented below (T5.3-5.6).

There has been extensive use of online dissemination since the beginning of the RAMONES project, which continued till the present day. The overall progress is summarized together with analytics, showing the use of both the website and the relevant social media channels to promote the vision of the RAMONES project and disseminate its results to a wider, multi-faceted audience.

2. Communication activities

2.1 Digital channels

2.1.1 RAMONES project website

The design and development of the RAMONES website (<https://ramones-project.eu/>) was presented in the deliverable “D5.23 Website, Social Media” on M1 and its final release with some additions was presented in the document “D5.15 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2”. In the present deliverable, more additions and renewals have been made in the website such as dissemination material, deliverables, events, training etc. Moreover, on the home page two more home buttons have been added, dedicated to the “RAMONES Summer School” and “RAMONES Hackathon”, leading to other external links created for these two events. These buttons on the home page of the website are helpful for the users because they provide direct links to the event webpages, saving time that would otherwise be spent browsing through tabs.

The following Figures show screenshots of the latest content added in the website.

Figure 1 - The renewed RAMONES website, now featuring the “RAMONES Summer School” and “RAMONES Hackathon” buttons in the main home page.

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NEWS Archives – RAMONES Project

EVENTS • NEWS

RAMONES Hackathon Achieves Great Success!

11 December 2024

The RAMONES Hackathon at the NKUA Department of Physics on 5-12-24 was a huge success! The four competing teams comprised of students and young researchers excelled in various thematic areas, giving their best and creating very interesting presentations related to the challenges: Visualizing marine radioactivity data at a global or local scale, forecasting radioactivity based...

[READ MORE >](#)

EVENTS • HANDS-ON PRACTICAL TRAINING • NEWS

RAMONES Hackathon 2024

29 November 2024

The EU H2020 RAMONES project organizes jointly with the MSc Program in "Electronics and Radioelectrology, and Control and Computing", the MSc Program "Applied Physics" and the MSc Program "General Physics" its first Hackathon at the Department of Physics of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens in 4th and 5th of December 2024. Young researchers...

[READ MORE >](#)

NEWS

RAMONES Field Work in Santorini and Kolumbo

Figure 2 - Screenshots of the recent content added in the 'News Archives' sections of the website

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Figure 3 - Screenshot of the webpage of RAMONES Summer School

Metrics

The project's website serves as a continually evolving resource, receiving monthly updates that include recent developments, upcoming events, new publications, and project outputs. This site is dedicated to broadcasting the project's efforts and achievements, targeting a wide online audience ranging from stakeholders to the general public and beyond. Following the Google Analytics (GA) service which monitors the traffic of the website, yearly activity (M37-M48) of the website has been estimated and is highlighted below.

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Figure 4 - Website activity concerning users and page views. Google Analytics is used

In Fig. 5, a summary of the monthly project's activity between M37 and M48 and users' interaction with the website are presented in plots accompanied by statistics.

Moreover, the following resulting figures reflect the continuous and transversal work carried out by all partners during the fourth year of the project. Website activity is regularly monitored using Google Analytics for periodic assessment. Key metrics, including visitor locations, user activity over time and new users by primary channel group are analyzed and presented in the following figures. The data clearly demonstrate that the RAMONES project has captured global interest, particularly from the USA, Greece, France, the UK, Spain, Russia and Germany. Detailed insights into the website metrics can be found in the following figures. Notably, the trends reveal that RAMONES has successfully reached an international audience, with a cumulative curve of new users per month indicating consistent growth.

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Figure 5 - Overview of the New Users by primary channel group

Active users by Country

Figure 6 - Main visitors to RAMONES website per country

Figure 7 - User activity trending over time (M37-M48)

2.1.2 Story Map

The Story Map of RAMONES project is accessed through the website by the home button and has been extensively described in the previous deliverable D5.12 'Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3'. In this deliverable the information about the Santorini field tests were implemented together with photographs of the final experiments and instrumentation. Moreover, a map was created showing the locations of the tests performed with the novel instruments.

The story map is an effective tool to promote and introduce the project to a broad audience in a user-friendly and interactive way. The most important thing of the story map is the frequent updates with new content concerning the project's scope and activities. Specifically, new text, images, videos, maps with interactive content and additional multimedia files could be added.

The Story Map was implemented online in September 2023 (M33) after offline development and testing. It can be accessed through the link:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/391f0b5a0cc846039f49c0b6ff89ccc5>

Figure 8 - The welcome page of the renewed Story Map of the RAMONES project

The Story Map is organized across ten main tabs including information of the objectives of the project, marine radioactivity, project testing sites, instrumentation, field testings and connection to RAMONES social media. Screenshots of the story map updated material are depicted below.

Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3

RAMONES project

About Marine radioactivity Testing sites Milos site Santorini site Kolumbo site Instrumentation Testings Consortium Follow us

The glider's tests inside the caldera.

The deployment of the instruments in Exo Yalos port.

Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3

Figure 9 - Screenshots of the Story Map showing new material added referring to Santorini field tests

The RAMONES story map has collected close to 5 visits per month over a twelve-month span in the project's fourth year. During this specific period, the story map achieved 212 views. According to the following figure, a high peak (57 views) was observed in December when information about the Santorini field tests were added to the story map.

Figure 10 - Usage Trends: RAMONES Storymap Engagement and Peak View Analysis (Dec 2023-Dec 2024)

2.1.3 Social media channels

The RAMONES project has implemented a sophisticated social media strategy, utilizing five (5) social media channels - Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube. The scope of social media for the RAMONES project can be understood as a strategic tool to disseminate project information, engage stakeholders, and amplify the project's impact. In this final year of the project the activity in all the channels has been increased, as well as the impact to the audience. More posts have been made and the interaction with our followers has been boosted. Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn usually show a post per week.

The impact of the RAMONES project's social media presence in 2024 is referred to the quantitative impact (impressions, metrics, posts, etc), qualitative impact (awareness, engagement, scientific dissemination, etc) and analytics and insights.

During 2024 we increased the online presence of the project, to influence the scientific community, the general public and the stakeholders, and to share the knowledge we gained with our audience.

Tracking and metrics

On Facebook, an average of 4 posts per month were published, during a 12-month period in the third and fourth year of the project (M37-M48) with overall good impression and interaction indices. The Facebook page resonance during the fourth year of the project had an increase of 18,8% reaching 3,968 number of persons. The interaction with the content was also increased up to 25% reaching 759 interactions with the audience.

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Figure 11 - Summary of Facebook activity of the fourth year of the project (M37-M48)

Additional statistics about the Facebook page show a consequential/significant number of publications this year, with its total number reaching 44 and thus indicating an increase of 22%. This is fueled by the many additional activities conducted during the fourth year, such as fieldwork and tests of the instruments, the summer school, the hackathon, conferences etc. The visits on our page have also increased remarkably during the fourth year of the project reaching 81.3%.

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Post frequently and improve interaction with content

Publications **1**

44 ↑ 22,2%

Stories **1**

0 0%

Median interactions with Facebook posts **1**

13 ↑ 30%

Visits **1**

1.3 thousand ↑ 81,3%

Figure 12 - Overview of the statistical results during the fourth year of our project

Statistics about the age and gender of the followers on Facebook draw interesting inferences from the audience originating mostly from European countries (Greece, France, Netherlands, Portugal, Italy, Sweden, Switzerland, U.K, Spain) and the U.S.A. The Total number of followers is 528 and total likes are 479 almost the same number as the third year.

Figure 13 - An estimation of the Facebook followers per gender

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Following are some of the posts:

The RAMONES Story map is now updated with new material! The Santorini site tab was added having information about the fieldtests performed, photos and an interactive map with more information of the testing sites.

Check this: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/.../391f0b5a0cc846039f49c0b6...>

#storymap #ramones_eu #environment #marine #ecosystem #ocean

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RAMONES EU

Δημοσιεύτηκε από Stevi Kazana

· 19 Δεκεμβρίου στις 11:43 π.μ. · 🌐

RAMONES partners had an excellent opportunity to work together for the final demos with all the novel instrumentation that were developed during the project in a real marine environment in Santorini, Greece!

So much excitement and anxiety for the tests! At the end of the two weeks of experiments everything went well and overall it was a successful mission!

Read more:

<https://ramones-project.eu/ramones-field-work-in.../>

#santorini #kolumbo #volcano #marine #... Δείτε περισσότερα

RAMONES-PROJECT.EU

RAMONES Field Work in Santorini and Kolumbo

Between sea and shore, sun and wind, salt and sand, the RAMONES team have gathered in full...

Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3

RAMONES EU

Δημοσιεύτηκε από Stevi Kazana

· 9 Δεκεμβρίου στις 12:21 μ.μ. · 🌐

🎉👏 The RAMONES Hackathon at the NKUA Department of Physics on 5-12-24 was a huge success! The four competing teams comprised of students and young researchers excelled in various thematic areas, giving their best and creating very interesting presentations related to the challenges: Visualizing marine radioactivity data at a global or local scale, forecasting radioactivity based on existing or simulated time series of data, forecasting seismic data based on historic and onli... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

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RAMONES EU

Δημοσιεύτηκε από Stevi Kazana

· 18 Οκτωβρίου ·

RAMONES (NTUA partners) conducted tests of the glider in Greece before the final expedition to Santorini and Kolumbo underwater volcano, where all the instruments will work together on monitoring radioactivity in the ocean environment!

#Corinthian_gulf #glider #H2020 #Innovation #Kolumbo #volcano #marine_environment #monitoring #novel_technology #ocean_ecosystems #radioactivity #ramones_eu #sniffer #tests <https://ramones-project.eu/ramones-tests-the-glider-in.../>

Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3

Figure 14 - Screenshots of the Facebook posts and reactions

Concerning the Instagram account, a total of 108 posts have been published on the Instagram account since the beginning of the project that promote our scope, daily activities, goals and

Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3

achievements. The Instagram community is expanding reaching a total of 97 followers and 50 interactions with the content. This year (M37-M48) a statistical analysis of the instagram channel follows:

Figure 15 - Summary of Instagram activity of the fourth year of the project (M37-M48)

Finally, the Instagram visits increased during the fourth year compared to the third year of the project by 150%, with a total of 215 visits!

Figure 16 - Total visits of our Instagram page per month this year

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ramones_eu

Following

Message

+3 ...

108 posts

97 followers

54 following

RAMONES EU

RADioactivity Monitoring in Ocean EcosystemS is an EU-H2020-FET funded project bringing radical new tech solutions for... more

🌐 ramones-project.eu

Followed by tsoupress_blog, p_krassakis + 10 more

POSTS REELS TAGGED

Figure 17 - Screenshot of the Instagram page showing the latest posts and activity

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On X.com (prev. twitter), the project continued disseminating relevant information and results. In total, 323 posts have been published, with a recurrence of approximately one month between posts. As a result, 14 more posts have been published in the M37-M48 period. The channel kept its number of active followers receiving comments, retweets and likes for the RAMONES posts.

Figure 18 - Screenshots of the X.com (prev. twitter) page showing the latest posts and activity

Below is the X.com analytics for the period M37-M48 (the aggregate data are estimated from tracking individual posts, as X.com discontinued Analytics for the non-premium users during this reporting period and additionally disabled API functionality for third-party analytics services, which could be used to obtain analytical information).

X.com @ramones_eu (M37-M48)

users:	87
posts:	323
impressions:	10.8k

The analysis of the number of impressions to RAMONES twitter profile is an indication of how the project triggers interest, as well as the extent to which it is becoming known. The impact is closely linked to relevant events (such as the field tests of the RAMONES instruments), participation in events and congresses, other fairs and exhibitions, summer schools and training).

In the same reporting period M37-M48, the project disseminated information, results, and achievements on LinkedIn, as well. The social channel has a total number of 220 followers, a total of 20 new posts (total 67) receiving 500 new likes (total 1144). The total views have been raised by 6307 new impressions. See LinkedIn post impressions (Fig. 20), visitor engagement (Fig. 21) and samples of 2 posts on LinkedIn (Figs. 22 and 23).

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Content performance

6,307

Impressions

▲741% Past 365 days

Figure 19 - Post impressions for LinkedIn in M37-M48

138

Engagements

▲626.4% Past 365 days

Figure 20 - Visitor engagement with RAMONES LinkedIn posts in M37-M48

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Figure 21 - Sample LinkedIn post #1 (in greek)

Figure 22 - Sample LinkedIn post #2

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On YouTube, 2 new videos have been uploaded in the public domain during the period M37-M48, raising the total number of public videos in the RAMONES youtube channel to 15, see a sample screenshot in Fig. 24. With the new additions to the channel an aggregate number of 551 views has been recorded. A total of 17 subscribers (+1 in M37-M48) have been recorded. The following pictures show the metrics of YouTube, such as total subscribers/views (Fig. 25) and total impressions (Fig. 26).

Figure 23 - A sample extract of a public video available on the RAMONES youtube channel

Figure 24 - Subscribers and total views of the YouTube channel for M37-M48

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Figure 25 - Impressions of YouTube for M37-M48

In addition, a dedicated vimeo video concerning the final experimental field test in Santorini during October 2024 was produced and published in RAMONES blog and News accordingly:

<https://ramones-project.eu/ramones-in-santorini-video/>

Figure 26 - Screenshot of the vimeo video

Finally, in the final stage of the project again X/Twitter and Facebook are the main social media platforms that gather the most followers and impressions. LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube follow the other platforms, but still attract public attention and show rising trends.

2.1.4 Mailing & Newsletter activities

The RAMONES mailing list is a collection of email addresses of people that have subscribed to our newsletter through the project website or through the social media channels and story map. The mailing list is used for formal and official communication and is always open for new subscriptions to be added. During this final year of the project, the project's mailing list has grown and more young scientists and interested parties have been subscribed for the updates concerning the instrumentation, tests and other milestones.

Newsletters

As in the two first years of the projects, and in alignment with the initial committed biannual rate, two (2) newsletters have been published during the fourth year of the project (at M43 and M48). The newsletters comprise four articles each, which have been published in the RAMONES blog and are considered to have more suitable topics to the interests of the general public. The newsletters offer additional links to the full content of the website and social media channels. At the point of authoring this report, the number of subscribers has reached 559.

Following are some examples of the 7th and 8th newsletters of the final year of the project.

Happy Holidays and New Year wishes for 2025!

[Read more →](#)

Figure 27 - Examples of the RAMONES 7th and 8th Newsletters (continued to the next pages)

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RAMONES Hackathon Achieves Great Success!

The RAMONES Hackathon at the NKUA Department of Physics on 5-12-24 was a huge success! The four competing teams comprised of students and young researchers excelled in various thematic areas, giving their best and creating very interesting presentations related to the challenges: Visualizing marine radioactivity data at a global or local scale, forecasting radioactivity based on existing or simulated time series of data, forecasting seismic data based on historic and online data, and visualizing environmental data from the marine environment. The teams greatly collaborated to produce innovative ideas and interesting solutions!

[Read more →](#)

RAMONES Field Work in Santorini and Kolumbo

Between sea and shore, sun and wind, salt and sand, the RAMONES team have gathered in full assembly for the final demo trials in the volcanic island of Santorini in the second half of October.

The research team have optimized and deployed all technologies developed through the project timeline, paying attention to all critical details and fighting the harsh conditions being present inside the remote oceanic environment.

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Underwater glider field tests performed on the island of Poros

The RAMONES NTUA team conducted field tests using the Slocum G3 underwater glider on the island of Poros, Greece on the 6th and the 7th of April 2024. The team, led by Prof. Konstantinos Karantzas and consisting Dr. Valsamis Ntouskos, Christos Antoniou, Simon Vellas and Sotiris Spanos, conducted several test missions in the gulf of Vagionia located on the northern part of the island.

[Read more →](#)

RAMONES collaborates with the Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria

We are pleased to provide an update on our progress with the [RAMONES](#) project at the Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. Our current focus has been on preparing the A-TIRMA sail drone for upcoming experiments. Significant advancements have been made, including the installation of crucial communication and navigation components, ensuring readiness for remote operations. The electronics have been thoroughly tested and are operational, with the USBL/modem transducers from Evologics and the USBL electronics

3. Dissemination activities

3.1 Publishing activities (Articles and publications)

General interest articles can be disseminated through press outlets, media platforms, or the project's official website. The range of published materials encompasses general-purpose content, press releases, media features, and scientific publications. The project's website functions as the central repository for all generated content.

3.1.1 Articles of general and scientific purpose

The articles of scientific interest are 10 journal papers and 6 conference papers (all peer-reviewed):

Books

1. Reza Ghabcheloo and Antonio Pascoal, Editors, Motion Optimization and Control of Single and Multiple Autonomous Aerial, Land, and Marine Robots, Printed Edition of the Special Issue Published in Sensors, April 2023. ISBN 978-3-0365-6328-2.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/books978-3-0365-6329-9>
2. V. Cichella, I. Kaminer, A. Pascoal, N. Hovakymian, Editors, "Direct Methods for Optimal Control Using Bernstein Polynomials", to be published by Springer in 2025
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2. Siltzovalis G., Lagaki V., Madesis I. and Mertzimekis T.J., "Characterization of a CZT-based spectrometer for underwater operation via simulations and experiments", Journal of Instrumentation (Jinst) - IOPscience, Volume 19, May 2024,
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/19/05/P05008>
3. Krassakis P., Karavias A., Nomikou P., Karantzalos K., Koukouzas N., Athinelis I., Kazana S., Parcharidis I., "Multi-Hazard Susceptibility Assessment Using the Analytical

- Hierarchy Process in Coastal Regions of South Aegean Volcanic Arc Islands*”, GeoHazards 2023, 4(1), 77-106, <https://doi.org/10.3390/geohazards4010006>
4. Fois G.R., Kolovi S., Breton V., Pereda A., Chardon P., Vega D.L., Terray L., Maigne L., “GATE MARIM DB, a Monte Carlo database for dose assessment of microorganisms exposed to natural α -radioactivity”, Journal of Environmental Radioactivity, November 2024, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5023324>
 5. Siltzovalis, G., Lagaki, V., Madesis, I. et al. Simulating the response of a HPGe-based spectrometer for in situ, long-term operation near the seabed. Eur. Phys. J. Spec. Top. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjs/s11734-025-01478-2>
 6. B. Sabetghadam, R. Cunha, A. Pascoal, “Enforcing temporal and spatial separation constraints in multi-vehicle trajectory generation problems using Bernstein relaxation and refinement methods”, accepted for publication in IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters (RA-L), Jan. 2025.
 7. N. Hung, E. Cunha, F. Branco, A. Pascoal, “Target localization and pursuit with networked robotic vehicles: theory, simulation, and experiments,” accepted for publication in Journal of Field Robotics, online version available on 16 January 2025 <https://doi.org/10.1002/rob.22513>
 8. Y. Gong, Y. Li, F. Branco, M. Yuan, A. Pascoal, “A Precision Loop Closure Detection Technique for AUV Bathymetric SLAM in the Absence of a DVL,” accepted for publication in IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement, Dec. 2024
 9. Cristina Colado, Dictino Chaos, David Salinas, Antonio Pascoal “An Energy Efficient Fault-Tolerant Controller for Homing of Underactuated AUVs,” Control Engineering Practice, Vol. 146, May 2024, 105883 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conengprac.2024.105883>
 10. Jiqiang Li, Guoqing Zhang, Antonio Pascoal, David Cabecinhas, “Prescribed performance path following control of USVs via an output based threshold rule,” IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, Vol. 73, Issue 5. May 2024 <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2023.3338518>
 11. Giovanna Rosa Fois, Sofia Kolovi, Vincent Breton, Alexis Pereda, Patrick Chardon, Dariana Llanes Vega, Luca Terray, Lydia Maigne, “GATE MARIM DB, a Monte Carlo

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1. Siltzovalis G., Madesis I., Lagaki V., Mertzimekis T.J., Krassakis P., Kazana S., and Nikolopoulos K., "Exploring the hydrothermal vent field of Milos Island in Aegean Sea using novel radiation instrumentation", EGU General Assembly 2024, <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU24/EGU24-10152.html>
2. Antoniou C., Spanos S., Vellas S., Ntouskos V., and Karantzas K., "StreamUR: Physics-informed Near Real-Time Underwater Image Restoration", The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, 48, 1-8, 2024
<https://isprs-archives.copernicus.org/articles/XLVIII-3-2024/1/2024/>
3. Chatsikian M., Ntouskos V., Mallios A., and Karantzas K., "Neural-based reconstruction of radioactivity distribution in large water volumes with underwater gliders", 10th Italian Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Robotics, 2024
<https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3686/paper1.pdf>
4. Mallios, Angelos, et al. "Underwater glider custom payload for long-term radioactivity measurements." Instrumentation viewpoint 23 (2024): 70-71.
5. Kakogeorgiou I., Gidaris S., Karantzas K., and Komodakis, N., "SPOT: Self-Training with Patch-Order Permutation for Object-Centric Learning with Autoregressive Transformer", IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 22776-22786), 2024
6. Efthymiadis N., Psomas B., Laskar Z., Karantzas K., Avrithis Y., Chum O., and Toliadis G., "Composed Image Retrieval for Training-Free Domain Conversion". IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV), 2025 (to appear)

Conference contributions (no proceedings)

1. Mallios, Angelos, et al. "Towards radioactivity monitoring in confined environments." International Underwater Glider Conference 2024, Gothenburg Sweden, June 10-14

2. Camilli Richard, et al. "Under-ice Assessment of the Arctic Marginal Ice Zone with an Autonomous Underwater Glider." International Underwater Glider Conference 2024, Gothenburg Sweden, June 10-14

PhD Theses

1. G. Siltzovalis (NKUA Physics), "*Simulations and optimization of an innovative spectrometer for in situ radioactivity monitoring in ocean ecosystems*" (to be defended in April 2025).

Master's Theses

1. V. Pedro, "*Optimal Path Planning for Radiation Detection with Autonomous Underwater Gliders*", Master's Thesis, Instituto Superior Técnico, 2024
2. D. Akanji, "*Cooperative Motion Control and Navigation of Autonomous Marine Vehicles for Ocean Observation*", Master's Thesis, Instituto Superior Técnico, 2024
3. A. Karadimas, "*Radioactivity risk estimation in the marine environment*", Master's thesis, NKUA (2024)

3.1.2 White papers

1. V. Lagaki, G. Siltzovalis, I. Madesis, P. Vasileiou, T.J. Mertzimekis, "*Monitoring of the radioactivity in the marine environment: a White Paper - Part I*", NUCET 10, 179 (2024), doi: 10.3897/nucet.10.133710

3.2 Invited talks and lectures

The invited lectures listed below include topics that were inspired by and cover many of the topics addressed in the scope of the RAMONES project:

1. Ntouskos M., "*Online invited talk of AI*", Brunel Center, 20.03.2024.
2. Mertzimekis T.J., "*Energy cocktail and the energy of the stars*", Webinar at Tech University of Crete, School of Mineral Resources Engineering, 05.03.2024 (in greek)
3. Mertzimekis T.J., "*Atoms and Radioactivity, from stars to the depths of the oceans*", "Apostolos Pavlos" High School Thessaloniki, 25.09.2024 (in greek)
4. Mallios A., Invited lecture at ERASMUS MUNDUS JOINT MASTER in Intelligent Field Robotic Systems, University of Girona, Spain.
5. A. Pascoal, Exploring the Blue Frontier with Cooperative Marine Robots, CSIE Workshop, Innovations in Autonomous Systems, Terevan, Armenia, Oct. 6, 2024.

6. A. Pascoal, Applications of Marine Robotics to Science and Ocean Literacy, VIII Workshop Sea and Atmosphere, Univ. Aveiro, Portugal, 28 Feb. 2024.
7. A. Pascoal, Cooperative Marine Robotics, a 2-day course for MSc students at the Univ. Toulon, France, May 21-22 May, 2024.

Event organization

1. Organization of Methana Summer Datathon, 03-07.07.2024, Greece
<https://sites.google.com/view/env-intel-school/home>

The organisation of the Summer School on Environmental Intelligence was a very successful event focusing on innovative solutions for radioactivity monitoring, marine robotics, marine engineering, AI & big data in environmental science, climate change & sustainability. The school attracted graduate and postgraduate students, early-career scientists & academics. The school aimed to:

- ❖ Activate new approaches for monitoring, analysing, and managing critical resources in Europe.
- ❖ Monitor environmental radioactivity in marine environments with state-of-the-art detection technology.
- ❖ Ensure the availability of reliable data and models at multiple levels of detail for making environmental policy decisions.
- ❖ Reduce the environmental footprint of environmental ICT.
- ❖ Explore the role of artificial intelligence in risk forecasting.
- ❖ Increase local and individual/citizen awareness of environmental impacts.

The purpose of the summer school was achieved as participation exceeded expectations and the eagerness to learn among participants was intense both during the lectures and in the field measurements. The school promoted science but additionally created prospects for its further dissemination among young scientists.

Figure 28 - The poster of the 2024 RAMONES Summer School

Figure 29 - Group photo of the Summer School 2024 participants with representatives of the local authorities

2. Organization of Santorini instruments presentation, 24.10.24, Greece

The RAMONES team have gathered in full assembly for the final demo trials in the volcanic island of Santorini. The research team has optimized and deployed all technologies developed through the project timeline, paying attention to all critical details and fighting the harsh conditions being present inside the remote oceanic environment. The main objective of the work was the deployment of the autonomous marine robotic instruments next to the fully loaded with other radiation-sensing and radiation-imaging instruments benthic laboratory. In an open public event the RAMONES team had the opportunity to work with local authorities informing them of the innovative technology the team has developed, as well as offer training and education to high-schoolers who had the opportunity to see, touch and feel the RAMONES equipment, watch the teams during action and receive important knowledge for the solutions offered via novel technology and methods.

Figure 30 - RAMONES instruments during final trials in Santorini

3. Organization of RAMONES Hackathon, 04-05.12.24, Greece

<https://sites.google.com/view/ramones-hackathon-2024/>

The RAMONES project organized jointly with the MSc Program in "Electronics and Radioelectrology, and Control and Computing", the MSc Program "Applied Physics" and the MSc Program "General Physics" a Hackathon event at the Department of Physics of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. Four competing teams comprised of students and young researchers excelled in various thematic areas, giving their best and creating very interesting presentations related to the challenges: Visualizing marine radioactivity data at a global or local scale, forecasting radioactivity based on existing or simulated time series of data, forecasting seismic data based on historic and online data, and visualizing environmental data from the marine environment. The teams greatly collaborated to produce innovative ideas and interesting solutions!

4. Collaborative engineering public trials with representatives from ROC-SIANI, IST and NTUA, 22-27.07.2024, Canary Islands, Spain

Figure 31 - Group photo of the trial in Canary Islands

5. Engineering public trials with IST team, September 2024, Ferreira do Zêzere, Portugal

Figure 32 - RAMONES instruments during trials in Portugal

Figure 33 - Announcement banner of RAMONES Hackathon

In addition, the RAMONES team actively supported and participated in two more hackathon events (*Apps4Athens* 30-31.03.2024 and *Plastic Fantastic* 17-18/04/2024), exploiting and presenting the outcomes of the project, providing the opportunity to the participants to engage in the RAMONES challenges and innovative work.

Figure 34 - Ms. Eleni Petra with participants and organizers at the Apps4Athens Hackathon (30-31.03.2024)

3.3 Meetings

During the reporting period (M37-M48), the RAMONES team conducted numerous meetings, predominantly via teleconference. Several sessions involving key stakeholders and policymakers were organized. Such meetings included briefings of the board members of the Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society and CNRS Executive Officers. In addition, on the side of international conferences IAEA officers were updated on RAMONES actions and results (RAP2024, ANP2024). These meetings provided an opportunity to present RAMONES, discuss innovation and business strategies, and address the challenges posed by emerging technologies and services.

3.4 Scientific events

The RAMONES team participated in workshops and attended several conferences during the fourth year of the project to present the scientific goals and the results of the project.

Table 1 - Scientific Workshops and conferences participated by RAMONES

Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
2nd RAMONES Workshop	Workshop	organisation	Athens, Greece, 17-18/01/2024
Industry CoP - Community Building Session	Workshop	presentation	EIC, 21/02/2024
MARTECH - The 11th International Workshop on Marine Technology	Workshop	presentation	University of Balearic Islands, Mallorca, Spain, 06-07/06/2024
RAP 2024	Conference	presentation	Granada, Spain, 10-12/06/2024
IUGC2024 - International Underwater Glider Conference 2024	Conference	presentation	Reveljen, Gothenburg, Sweden, 10-14/06/2024
IEEE IGARSS - International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium 2024	Conference	presentation	Megaron, Athens, Greece, 07-12/07/2024
EPS International Conference of Applied Nuclear Physics	Conference	presentation	Thessaloniki, Greece, 23-27/09/2024
NTUAREN European Researchers Night	Public Event	presentation	Athens, Greece, 27/09/2024

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Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
6th International Conference on Radioecology & Environmental Radioactivity ICRER 2024	Conference	presentation	Marseille, France, 24-29/11/2024
Exploring the Blue Frontier with Cooperative Marine Robots, CSIE Workshop, Innovations in Autonomous Systems	Workshop	presentation	Terevan, Armenia, 6/10/2024
Applications of Marine Robotics to Science and Ocean Literacy, VIII Workshop Sea and Atmosphere	Workshop	presentation	Univ. Aveiro, Portugal, 28/2/2024
Cooperative Marine Robotics, a 2-day course for MSc students	Course	presentation	Univ. Toulon, France, 21-22/5/2024
Encontro de Oceanografia 2024 [Oceanography Meeting] https://ciencias.ulisboa.pt/pt/encontro/03-05-2024/encontro-de-oceanografia-2024	Conference	presentation	Peniche, Portugal, 3-4/5/2024
EMRA 2024 - Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications https://emra-24.marinerobotics.eu	Workshop	presentation	Arenzano, Italy, 27-29/5/2024

Figure 35 - Dr. Angelos Mallios (PLOATECH) at MARTECH 2024

Figure 36 - RAMONES WP6 leader, Eleni Petra (NKUA), presented the 88th Thessaloniki International Fair

4. Summary

As a conclusion, the following table summarizes the indicators of success of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. The details are presented in the Report of Activities section above.

1. KPI's concerning user attraction up to the 48th month of the project (completion of the project):

Table 2 - KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Workshops / conferences (co)organized.	6	12	200%
Ecosystem	Workshops supported by presenters and panelists on project specific topics.	14	25	179%

2. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination:

Table 3 - KPIs concerning scientific dissemination

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Average technical blog posts per year	2	2	100%
Ecosystem	Peer reviewed scientific publications	10	59	590%
Ecosystem	Other scientific publications and artifacts	12	18	150%
Ecosystem	References and acknowledgements	50	164	328%
Ecosystem	Whitepapers (as per work plan)	3	1	33%
Ecosystem	Multimedia & training material published	8	8	100%
Ecosystem	Percentage of Open Access publications	>70%	90%	100%
Wide range	Fairs and exhibitions participated	3	14	467%
Wide range	Commercial exploitation events participation	5	5	100%

3. KPIs concerning social dissemination:

Table 4 - Table 4 KPIs concerning social dissemination

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Websites launched (workplan)	1	1	100%

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Wide range	Website content updating (average)	monthly	monthly	100%
Ecosystem	Templates for dissemination activities and other material	2	2	100%
Wide range	Average general public blog posts per year	6	6	100%
Ecosystem	Hardcopy/tangible material forms	3	8	267%
Wide range	Social media dissemination channels	4	5	125%
Wide range	Social media impressions (social media channels total)	10000	56184	562%
Wide range	Social media followers (total across media)	1200	952	79%
Wide range	Average social media posts per month	2	4.5	225%
Wide range	General public articles languages supported	4	3	75%
Wide range	General public articles on printed or online media	8	7	88%
Wide range	Newsletters issued (biannual)	8	8	100%

4. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts:

Table 5 - KPIs concerning strengthening impact via joint efforts

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Relevant H2020 Projects & other projects liaised with RAMONES	6	19	317%
Ecosystem	MoUs signed with 3rd parties.	5	5	100%
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons organized by the project	2	2	100%
Ecosystem	3rd party datathons/hackathons supported by project	2	2	100%
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons participants	200	396	198%
Ecosystem	Individuals directly addressed via scientific, academic communication, innovation stimulation, training and engagement activities	1800	221965	12331%